

Future Trends of Multimedia In Education

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Abstract. Following the Covid-19 pandemic that is currently afflicting the worldwide, multimedia can be considered a highly significant medium and instrument in many areas, particularly education. Previously, students and educators engaged in face-to-face teaching and learning at school or universities, but as a result of the pandemic, students and educators have been exposed to online learning. Based on the research from the articles, it states some point of view towards multimedia in education. It gives a clear explanation about advantages and disadvantages of multimedia in education. In other hand, it also states challenges and future of multimedia technology.

Keywords: COVID-19 Pandemic, Online Learning, Education.

Introduction

It is impossible to discuss the role of multimedia in the future of education without considering the future of education at all levels. The issues are wide-ranging, and there is no evidence to date that there is a fool proof solution that educators can use. This is also unlikely to occur. Furthermore, there is little agreement among educators about the future structure and function of educational institutions serving the various sectors. Predicting the role of multimedia in such an uncertain environment would be, to say the least, ambitious. However, by implementing a suitable set of principles, educators can set themselves some viable targets that are less susceptible to the erratic changes in technology (Radford, 1997). Especially in this Covid-19 pandemic era, students nowadays have their lessons 'online,' and educators will provide their students with online learning such as in PowerPoint slides or recorded lessons so that students do not fall behind in online learning. When discussing the role of multimedia in education, it is obvious that debates that focus on technological ability rather than pedagogical strategy will yield little useful information; achievement of machines, software, and programmers rather than achievement of learners and mentor rather

than quality of learning experiences and outcomes (Radford, 1997). That is not to say that technological parameters and achievements are unimportant. They are essential as long as you have appropriate educational strategies, goals, experiences, and outcomes to which they can be directed. In this term paper, we will go over Future Trends of Multimedia in Education in greater depth. Throughout this term paper, we will discuss the advantages and disadvantages of multimedia in education, as well as the challenges and future of multimedia technology.

Definition of Multimedia

There are many opinions expressed by researchers regarding the definition of multimedia. Multimedia is the presentation of text, images, audio, and video with links and tools that allow the user to navigate, engage, create and communicate using a computer. In other words, multimedia can be defined as numerous media elements combined into one whole subject, which produces fruitful outcomes for its end user. All these media elements are making communication more organized and clear than ever before (Pulasthi & Gunawardhana, 2016). There are two type classification in multimedia, Linear Multimedia and Non-Linear Multimedia. Linear Multimedia is a form of multimedia that is intended to be viewed in a predictable manner. It has a define start and finish. It follows a logical path from the beginning to the end. Linear multimedia tools usually move from one screen to another and are usually used by teachers as an additional teaching tool (Prostova et al., 2021). The main aims of Linear Multimedia include entertain, impart knowledge and familiarise people with a certain topic without any distractions. Example of the Linear Multimedia is a PowerPoint presentation, a storyline, a YouTube video and an anime episode. Non-Linear Multimedia is a nonsequential kind of multimedia that relies heavily on the user's participation. The individual must engage with a computer programme in this form of media, putting him in charge of the experience. When used as active learning tools, non-linear multimedia engages students in the use of 21st-century skills, which fall into six different categories, i.e. critical thinking, information and media literacy, creativity, communication skills, collaboration, and contextual learning (Prostova et al., 2021). Example of Non-Linear Multimedia include a website, a search engine's home page, a YouTube channel and an anime or Korean drama streaming site.

Advantages of Multimedia in Education

When we discussed the advantages of multimedia in education, as we all know that multimedia is very important and useful in education even before the Covid-19 pandemic occurs. As the role of educational multimedia expands, it is becoming increasingly important to understand the potential it provides for teaching and learning (Slack, 1999). Educators rarely use traditional learning methods such as books, writing, and so on (Baharuddin et al., 2021). Most educators use multimedia in

their learning classes, such as PowerPoint slides, E-books, graphics images, music, sound, videos, records, films, animations, and more. Multimedia creates a technologically advantageous learning environment (Neo & Neo, 2009). The computer is widely used for a variety of reasons, including the ability to make jobs easier, more accurate, more effective, and faster, among other benefits. The advancement of computer technology has resulted in the advancement of many other technologies such as digital television, mobile phones, networks, internet, audio and video devices, and so on (Baharuddin et al., 2020). The obvious point is that this technology has become accessible to people of all ages. It is critical to include computers in education to deal with the increased widespread adoption of these technologies (Bahera & Nayef, 2015). Traditional teaching methods and aids are no longer effective in the modern era. As a result, using multimedia in education has become a must these days in order to improve the teaching and learning experience. To deal with the increased widespread adoption of these technologies, it is critical to incorporate computers into education. Traditional teaching methods and aids are no longer effective in today's world. On the other hand, using multimedia in education has become a necessity in order to improve the teaching and learning process.

Multimedia content helps to vary and enhance the learning process, resulting in better knowledge retention. More opportunities for students to engage with the content can be provided by educational video. Video-based course content can be beneficial to students from all over the world. Using multimedia in education allows educators to engage students while also allowing students to be more involved and retain more information from the lesson (Bahera & Nayef, 2015). In today's fast-paced society, students are constantly bombarded with technology and are accustomed to receiving knowledge and information immediately. The use of multimedia in education has also increased problem solving. We are highly stimulated when we absorb images, video, and animations alongside text because a large portion of our brain is reserved for processing visual information. As a result, student attentiveness and information retention improve. Students can solve problems by relying on themselves, which is known as the self-exploration method, collaboration, and active participation. In a planned manner, media materials such as still and animated graphics, video and audio, as well as simulations and models, are integrated. These tools make it much easier to learn new information. It also aids students in their exploration of the world. This comes as no surprise. Children can use multimedia to explore and learn about places they would never visit otherwise. In a geography class, students can learn about the world's cities, the tallest mountains, and the most dangerous jungles. Exploration of space and planets is now possible in a science class. Dissection of unusual species and investigation of varied ecosystems are like a walk in the park in a biology class for students who benefit from a multimedia learning environment. In today's society, multimedia is critical since everything must keep up with the times. Multimedia is a wonderful medium of communication since it makes communicating and understanding what others are saying straightforward.

Disadvantages of Multimedia in Education

Apart from the advantages, there are also disadvantages of multimedia in education. The disadvantages of multimedia are not only to the educators, but it is also experienced by the students as well. Some observers have argued that technology in learning has widespread negative impact in the process of teaching and learning (Mantiri, 2014). Dehumanize teaching is one of the disadvantages of multimedia in education. Since the pandemic of Covid-19, students and educators have been instructed by the Ministry of Education to start online learning in their respective homes. This has led to the trend of “dehumanize teaching”. There are some educators believe that online learning does not burden the students, therefore they give a lot of homework and assignments to the students without considering the difficulties that students would experience in completing each assignment and homework. Many teachers and lecturers in instructional technology were treating students as if they are machines rather than human beings, according Mantiri (2014). Furthermore they argue that if teachers perceive learners as machines, they will treat them as such, with or without the use of instructional media (Mantiri, 2014). Although there have been many technological advancements in multimedia, instructors should put themselves in the shoes of students because not all students are able to use such quickly evolving technology due to financial, talent, and internet connection limits. This is because there are some students who live in rural areas and do not have strong internet ability to access multimedia software that requires strong internet support. Clear here that, it is very inappropriate if dehumanize teaching is practiced in education until it becomes a trend among educators out there.

Multimedia causes limited social interaction between students and educators in education. Because all students and educators only carry out online learning activities, it causes social interaction to be limited. Online students often engage peers in online discussions and interact with teachers via e-mail, this doesn't replicate the face-to-face experiences in a traditional classroom (Bahera & Nayef, 2015). In today's world, educators used YouTube and PowerPoint as a medium in learning for their students. This will cause there are some students who do not understands the topic discussed by the educator but they do not care about the matter because they think that watching the video recorded by the educator will make them understanding without asking what they do not understood to the educator. Student's performance will decline if they cannot answer the test conducted by the educator because they do not understand some of the topics that have been studied. Such incidents have demonstrated that social interaction between educator and students becoming increasingly limited. Despite the fact that multimedia technology is becoming more sophisticated and developing, face-to-face learning is more successfully since it allows for greater social interaction in the classroom.

Challenges and Future of Multimedia Technology

Multimedia in education has shown to be an efficient method for learning because of its ability to engage students, provide diverse types of content, and enhance the learning process. The educational world is still in relatively early stages with regards to the development and implementation of multimedia pedagogy into schools, however since there's been no changes in the market in recent years, it is highly likely that education trends will continue.

The benefits of multimedia in education are numerous; the most important being that it provides a way to engage students more effectively and to provide them with an engaging learning experience. The technology behind multimedia is usually not expensive, and furthermore, facilitates the learning process of students in various subjects such as science and history.

Multimedia also assures that students are able to perform tasks independently because they can access the necessary information from anywhere. One major issue facing education today is that there isn't enough money to go around, however, it is believed that multimedia will be able to solve this problem. Many universities are spending millions of dollars on computers and multimedia classrooms for students. This represents a huge investment for schools and universities to make because the technology is only used for short durations, which means that these school systems will have to spend the same amount of money annually if they choose not to switch over to multimedia.

As per mentioned earlier, multimedia is a combination of audio, images, or both (audio-visual content) and is a technique used to create media presentations (Flynn and Tetzlaff., 1998). Multimedia has been extensively applied in higher education for many years. It is now used in various activities such as teaching and learning, training and assessment, examination, presentation and communication. Multimedia has emerged as the most powerful tool for effective education and training. There has been a growth of the importance of the visual and auditory medium in education with the advent of ICT. Video is the visual part of multimedia; audio is the auditory part of the media. In recent years, the use of multimedia has become very popular in distance education. Multimedia is being used to create a variety of teaching tools. They can be used as stand-alone tools or as supplementary tools to provide extra content. The aim of multimedia in learning is to increase the retention of knowledge and to enhance the quality of the education. Students are attracted to audio-visual presentations due to their attractive visual and aural characteristics.

Multimedia technology has to address all of the components in coordination, since each component has evolved individually up to now. The sections that follow outline some of the primary obstacles that must be solved in order for modern multimedia applications to become as pervasive and impactful as we anticipate. The discussions were not designed to be exhaustive, instead, they're meant to point to important research projects that are discussed in this issue of the IBM Journal of Research and Development or that are now underway at IBM and elsewhere.

Network challenges

Network subsystems build distribution pathways and transfer media assets from multimedia servers to specific clients. Some media objects (e.g., huge video and audio files) are streamed isochronous from the servers to the clients to minimize long delay and the requirement for large client buffers (Dan et al., 1995). However, not every media transmission, such as when a user browses non-continuous media, necessitates isochronous streaming (e.g., text, image) according Dan (1995). The utilization of network technology and communication protocol stacks for multimedia data transfer clearly plays a key role in attaining the following objectives.

Minimization of data-transmission and data-reception overhead in order to conserve connection capacity for applications is one of the many issues in this area. These issues stem from data networking, where the severe latency requirements of video and audio, combined with the many standards that may be used on different networks, impose even harsher constraints. Latency is frequently significantly more critical than jitter in non-continuous, media-based systems, because it can alter the interactive reaction time. Given that one of the primary goals of multimedia applications is to provide services to users in the same way that phone service is provided, such as in kiosks and public multimedia terminals, in order to safeguard clients and maintain privacy, the network architecture must provide security at adequate levels. In such contexts, tamper-proof systems, effective authentication processes, and efficient and reliable delivery of encrypted data are all essential. Special attention must be made to the recovery of lost information in networks when information is transmitted encrypted and encoded for compression.

Client-design issues

The client's design will be dictated, as it always is, by questions of cost, functionality, and comfort (Dan et al., 1995). The client device can take several forms, including an upgraded television set (with internal or external "set-top" capability), an enhanced personal computer (a network computer with video capability), or a full-fledged personal computer. Higher functionality may be achievable if the control device is shared by all access devices in the family as part of a residence gateway, rather than if the circuitry must be reproduced in each of the many TVs in a residence.

For a few years, there will be pressure to limit the amount of RAM and video-processing power available, yet reducing buffer sizes and local computation will affect network load. (Highly compressed video, e.g., compression across many frames, cannot be handled by small buffers and poor processing capability). Prefetching and/or double buffering are also essential to ensure image quality, jitter reduction, and smoothing.) Many features are easier to execute if there is a lot of local secondary storage, but servicing moving parts, such as discs, in a home-video system could hurt sales.

Local limitations will undoubtedly determine which functions can be performed well locally and which require server or network help. Aside from the hardware issues

mentioned above, decisions about software interfaces, control paradigms, and operating systems, such as which functions will be static and which will be loaded with content or just when needed, will have a substantial impact on the client's cost and usability. A fixed set of capabilities is simple to manage, but it limits future updates and content kinds that can be viewed. Client devices are projected to become more difficult to use as multimedia applications advance from simple reply to complex search and simultaneous streams, and then to personalized settings. This will result in challenges with regard to optimizing resources and avoiding misbehavior and mischief, just as with current personal computers.

Application-design issues

Future multimedia apps will make use of useful and pleasurable data, such as various audio and video streams, as well as time, user, and data-dependent behaviors (Dan et al., 1995). Multiple applications working on the same data will need to manage information, evaluate photos, find relevant objects, and mesh live, pre-recorded, and interactive streams according to Dan (1995). Application developers must be able to easily design software that meets these and other requirements thanks to the software framework.

Developing complex content will become more difficult. It's never been easy to make videos that are enjoyable to watch. Advanced tools (for example, for generating multimedia material) will be necessary to mix numerous streams in appealing and impactful ways. However, addressing human perceptions and psychological effects of a composition will always remain the realm of creative artists (Baharuddin et al., 2019a). Image, audio, and video data searches are substantially more challenging than text searches, but the benefits can be significantly greater (Serpanos et al., 1998).

We must maximize the value received from a minimal quantity of computing due to practical factors. Through interactive and real-time situations, such as push technology, browsing, and interactive navigation in massive collections of multimedia material, the requirements become much more stringent. Even more difficult is managing regulated collaborations and teleconferences with many audios, video, and data sources. People will demand increasingly more complex composite moving media in the future, with complex limits on the position and timing of the many components.

Conclusion

Up to now, the lack of infrastructure for delivery of high-quality video, the weakness of supporting technologies for easy content creation, the absence of experience with the benefits of futuristic multimedia, and a variety of economic factors have impeded the widespread deployment of multimedia applications (Dan et al., 1995). These restrictions are being broken down by experience with video on the Web and the availability of the Internet for disseminating low- and medium-bandwidth items. People increasingly recognize the huge significance of mass multimedia technology use in promoting socially acceptable and financially beneficial outcomes. Future-

research about Multimedia, multimedia, communications, networks, software and hardware for our company. This paper is about the conclusion about future-research of technologies, methods and projects. The multimedia field is developing fast. It's interesting to see what the future brings. But it's not sure that the whole information technology will change to multimedia technology. What we have seen in the last years, the personal computer has changed to the mobile computer, the word processor has changed to a typing system (typing a word document has become more difficult). The electronic program-cassette has changed to the mobile, portable and wireless, so-called "netbook", that is much more powerful than the electronic program-cassette and can also be connected to an external device. It is still difficult to think about the future of the personal computer. However, the mobile computer (Smartphone, notebook, PDA) is already part of everyday life. And I believe it will continue to develop and grow.

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